

Stylish, Savage, Sarcastic: Exploring Sarcasm in *Cruella*

Muhammad Nasir^{1*}, Lia Salsabila², Uniansasmita Samoh³,

¹English Department, Fakultas Tarbiyah dan Keguruan, UIN Ar-Raniry, Banda Aceh, Indonesia

²English Department, Fakultas Tarbiyah dan Keguruan, UIN Ar-Raniry, Banda Aceh, Indonesia

³Prince of Sonkla University, Pattani Campus

ABSTRACT

This study examines how sarcasm is used in the 2021 film *Cruella*, focusing on its role in shaping the main character, Cruella. By analysing selected film scenes and dialogues through a qualitative descriptive approach, the research clarifies: (1) how sarcasm illustrates Cruella's defiance and critiques of social norms, (2) how it influences her relationships, and (3) the contribution of visual elements like costume and music in reinforcing sarcastic meanings. The study finds illocutionary sarcasm is most frequent, with propositional sarcasm least observed. Overall, Cruella uses sarcasm as a core strategy to build character complexity and deliver key themes of identity, rebellion, and societal expectations. The analysis aims to show how sarcasm is integrated across dialogue, symbolism, and narrative tone, providing insights for both film and linguistic studies.

Keywords: *Sarcasm, language, film, Cruella*

A. INTRODUCTION

Film, as a creative work, combines entertainment with narratives, values, and meanings. It shares with literature the role of presenting texts in various forms, often conveying moral messages, using visuals, and addressing culture and language.

Language is fundamental in film, serving as a vehicle for emotional expression and as a complementary means of communication alongside visual cues. Sitti Rabiah (2018) defines language as a tool for interaction through which thoughts, ideas, concepts, and feelings are conveyed. Similarly, Oktaviani (2024) notes that language helps audiences understand fictional characters. Thus, language in film constructs and delivers meaning to viewers.

The language used in film reflects characters' behaviours, attitudes, and identities. Adinata, Ayu, and Widiadnya (2025) state that language in film enables interaction by allowing characters to express thoughts, emotions, and intentions that shape relationships and guide audience interpretation. Dialogue analysis reveals the film's underlying messages and themes.

Within the framework of these communicative functions, one notable linguistic

phenomenon frequently employed in film dialogue is sarcasm. Sarcasm is a rhetorical device characterised by the use of expressions that contradict their literal meaning, typically serving as a form of indirect criticism or admonition that may cause offence to the recipient. Du, He, and Chu (2024) explain that sarcasm can be conveyed through multiple communicative signals, including contextual, verbal, and paralinguistic (nonverbal) cues. Its use often involves a combination of intonation, facial expression, and lexical choice, all of which contribute to the intended sarcastic meaning. Hardiati (2018) observes that sarcasm creates a dualistic interaction between the speaker, as the subject, and the recipient, as the object, in which the speaker derives satisfaction and aesthetic value, while the recipient tends to perceive the aesthetic value of sarcasm negatively.

The interpretation of sarcasm, however, is not uniform. Responses to sarcasm may vary depending on several factors, such as the speaker's intonation, body language, conversational context, the interpersonal relationship between the speaker and the listener, and the listener's familiarity with the speaker's sarcastic tendencies (Olsen, 2015). Abd-Alsajad and Ahmed (2021) describe sarcasm as an indirect and expressive speech act, often realised through verbal irony or ironic behaviour, by which speakers convey a strongly negative attitude toward their interlocutors. Additionally, Ali et al. (2023) suggest that sarcasm is frequently employed to attract attention and intensify the expression of negative sentiments. Historically, sarcasm has also been used as a means of psychological manipulation, potentially causing mental distress to its targets (Kadhim & Mewada, 2023).

In the realm of cinematic discourse, these varied responses to sarcasm mirror its broader functions in everyday communication, contributing not only to a film's aesthetic quality but also to its entertainment value. Riandika and Pasaribu (2025) argue that sarcasm in film plays a significant role in shaping interpersonal relationships among characters and in directing narrative development. When employed strategically in dialogue and visual scenes, sarcasm can deepen audience engagement and add layers of complexity and interpretative richness to the narrative. Within filmmaking, figurative language—including sarcasm—serves as a vital rhetorical device through which implicit meanings, social commentary, and critique may be conveyed.

To illustrate these concepts, *Cruella* (2021), a live-action adaptation centred on the iconic character Cruella de Vil from *101 Dalmatians*, narrates the transformation of Estella, an orphaned young woman with exceptional talent in fashion design and a strong sense of individuality. In her pursuit of success in the elite, highly competitive fashion industry, Estella constructs an alter ego, Cruella, that enables her to express her rebellious and transgressive impulses. The film received a generally positive critical reception, with particular praise for its performances, visual style, and costume design. Notably, *Cruella* won the Academy Award for Best Costume Design at the 94th Academy Awards, as well as Best Performance by a Young Actor at the Saturn Awards, and received several additional nominations, including for costume design, hair and makeup.

This study aims to clearly identify and categorise the types of sarcasm used in Cruella, focusing on their communicative functions within the film's narrative. By examining how characters deliver sarcasm and its impact on character portrayal, plot, and thematic development, the study offers clear insights into the narrative power of sarcasm as a linguistic and stylistic device. It also seeks to expand scholarly discussion on humour and figurative language in film adaptations.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Sarcasm

The term sarcasm originates from the Greek word *sarcazein*, meaning “to tear flesh,” which metaphorically refers to sharp mockery or biting ridicule. In linguistic terms, sarcasm is commonly understood as a figure of speech that employs irony to express contempt, ridicule, or criticism toward an individual or situation. Rather than conveying meaning directly, sarcastic utterances typically express an intention that is opposite to their literal interpretation and are often delivered in a caustic or bitter tone.

Sukarto and Fauziah (2022) explain that sarcasm combines a literal expression of praise or approval with an implied meaning that contradicts the contextual reality. This contrast between surface meaning and intended message is what enables sarcasm to function as a powerful communicative strategy. More broadly, sarcasm serves multiple pragmatic purposes, including humour, social criticism, and emphasis. Katyayan and Joshi (2019) identify three primary functions of sarcasm: as a form of witticism, as a vehicle for complaint, and as a means of indirect avoidance, allowing speakers to convey criticism without overt confrontation.

1.1. Types of Sarcasm

Camp (2011) classifies sarcasm into four major types: illocutionary sarcasm, lexical sarcasm, propositional sarcasm, and sarcasm prefaced with 'like'. Each type reflects a distinct pragmatic mechanism for conveying sarcastic meaning.

1.1.1. Illocutionary Sarcasm

Illocutionary sarcasm refers to sarcastic expressions in which the speaker's illocutionary force—the intended communicative act—contradicts the literal meaning of the utterance. Puji, Woi, and Juita (2022) describe this type of sarcasm as harsh or mocking remarks directed toward an individual or group, often designed to provoke a reaction. In such cases, the underlying intention of the statement is more significant than its explicit wording.

Abdullah, Adek, and Putra (2022) emphasise that illocutionary force plays a crucial

role in revealing hidden meanings in narratives, as sarcasm relies heavily on implication rather than direct expression. Illocutionary sarcasm operates at the level of speech acts and can express emotions such as praise, sympathy, or politeness while simultaneously conveying criticism or disapproval through contextual cues.

1.1.2. Lexical Sarcasm

Lexical sarcasm operates at the level of word choice and typically involves the use of positive lexical items to convey negative meanings, or vice versa. According to Puji et al. (2022), this form of sarcasm occurs when seemingly favourable expressions are employed to express dissatisfaction or criticism. Fadilah and Agus Wijayanto (2024) further argue that lexical sarcasm often appears within normative social relationships, where sarcastic expressions are embedded in everyday interactions.

This type of sarcasm tends to sound natural and fluent, making it commonly used—often unconsciously—in daily conversation. Although the lexical items themselves may be positive, their contextual use signals disappointment or disapproval. Lexical sarcasm is generally assertive in nature and frequently relies on exaggerated or extreme expressions that contrast with expected normative scales.

1.1.3. Propositional Sarcasm

Propositional sarcasm is considered one of the most explicit forms of sarcasm, as the contradiction between literal meaning and intended message is immediately apparent. Ramadhan and Setiasari (2023) associate this type of sarcasm with satire, as speakers deliberately produce statements that are clearly opposite to what they believe or intend to communicate.

Maula and Muhayani (2022) argue that propositional sarcasm occurs when a speaker utters propositions that directly contradict factual truth. Similarly, Shellydyriani and Munandar (2021) note that this form of sarcasm targets the propositional content of an utterance, making the sarcastic intent relatively direct and accessible to the listener, despite its ironic nature.

1.1.4. Sarcasm with the Prefix “Like”

Sarcasm prefixed with like shares similarities with propositional sarcasm but exhibits a more explicit form of rejection or disbelief. This type of sarcasm involves the use of the word like preceding a declarative statement, signalling that the speaker strongly rejects the proposition being expressed. Puji et al. (2022) explain that the presence of like allows listeners to quickly recognise the sarcastic intent, as it

functions as a pragmatic marker of teasing or mockery.

However, sarcasm with the prefix 'like' can also generate ambiguity, as the interpretation of 'like' depends heavily on context, intonation, and shared knowledge between the speaker and the listener. As a result, this form of sarcasm carries a greater risk of misunderstanding.

2. Film

Film, or cinema, is a widely consumed form of audio-visual media that enables audiences to engage with imaginative narratives and constructed realities. As a medium, film combines visual imagery, sound, dialogue, and narrative structure to create immersive storytelling experiences. Films attract global audiences through diverse genres, themes, and cultural representations.

Afdilila (2015) asserts that film, as an audiovisual text, is produced within specific social, historical, and cultural contexts that influence both its form and meaning. Consequently, films offer multiple analytical dimensions, including narrative structure, cinematography, sound design, setting, technological techniques, and character interaction. These elements collectively contribute to the film's communicative power and interpretative richness.

Hikma and Mahmud (2023) argue that film functions as an audiovisual communication medium through which messages are conveyed to a collective audience. As a cultural artefact, film can be regarded as a form of literature that encapsulates historical narratives, stories, cultural values, events, and knowledge. These elements are recorded in audiovisual form and disseminated through various platforms, such as television, cinema, theatres, and other broadcast media, primarily for entertainment, while also serving educational and communicative functions.

2.1. Cruella Film

Cruella is a 2021 American crime comedy film directed by Craig Gillespie. It serves as a reinterpretation of the iconic character Cruella de Vil from 101 Dalmatians. The film centres on Estella Miller, an intelligent and ambitious young woman determined to establish herself as a fashion designer. Emma Stone stars as the titular character, supported by Emma Thompson, Joel Fry, Paul Walter Hauser, Emily Beecham, Kirby Howell-Baptiste, and Mark Strong.

Set in 1970s London during the punk rock movement, the narrative follows Estella's

journey as she navigates the highly competitive and elitist fashion industry. To express her rebellious nature, Estella adopts an alter ego, Cruella, allowing her to explore her darker side. Her pursuit of success leads her into conflict with Baroness von Hellman, a celebrated yet ruthless fashion designer. Their rivalry forms the central conflict of the film, presented through a storyline rich in drama, irony, and sarcasm, making it particularly relevant for linguistic and pragmatic analysis.

2.2. Previous Research

A number of previous studies have examined the use of sarcasm in films and television series, providing valuable theoretical and methodological references for this research. Melawati (2022) found that characters in the film *Venom* frequently employ sarcasm in their dialogue, focusing on the types of sarcasm used and audience responses to sarcastic utterances.

Ramadhan and Setiasari (2023) analysed sarcasm in the television series *Friends*, identifying its types and purposes. Their findings revealed five primary functions of sarcasm: sophistication, evaluation, politeness, persuasiveness, and retractability.

Similarly, Padmatantri and Sutrisno (2021) investigated sarcastic utterances in *The Simpsons* using Camp's and Leech's theories to classify the types and functions of sarcasm present in the dialogue. Ayuningtyas and Triyono (2022) examined the use of satirical language in the short film *Tilik*, concluding that satire is employed by filmmakers to emphasise messages and clarify meaning for the audience, particularly through the character Tejo.

More recently, Septyanasari (2024) explored the types and functions of sarcasm in the 2023 *Barbie* film using a qualitative approach and Spradley's ethnographic analysis model. The study found that illocutionary sarcasm was the most frequently used type, while conveying commands emerged as the dominant function of sarcasm in the film.

C. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a qualitative descriptive method combined with the theory of sarcasm proposed by Camp (2011). Qualitative descriptive is used to analyse the data obtained as described below:

1. Research Approach

The present study focuses on the following types of sarcasm: lexical sarcasm, prepositional sarcasm, sarcasm that begins with the word "like," and illocutionary sarcasm. Research employed a data analysis approach, using a qualitative descriptive method to analyse the types of sarcasm in the film *Cruella*. (Robert C. Bogdan & Sari Knopp Biklen, 1982) argue that qualitative research is descriptive in nature, with

collected data expressed in words or pictures rather than numerical values. Consequently, the analysis of qualitative research involves the use of descriptive language. (NormanK.Denzin2018)Also, add that qualitative research is a multi-method research approach, involving interpretation and a naturalistic approach to its subject matter. Qualitative methods are considered easier because researchers use words to describe data. (JohnW. Creswell 2007) state that qualitative research is the process of collecting and analysing data using language rather than numbers. The objectives of this research are to analyse the types of sarcasm used and the functions of sarcasm in the film Cruella. The purpose of the research can be met by using tools, collecting data, and interpreting the results. (Walliman 2021) states that the results of qualitative research design are in the form of words that contain explanations, views, and descriptions. The utilisation of a descriptive qualitative approach is well-suited to this research, as it requires the analysis and description of sarcastic statements and dialogues in their verbal form. Employing this method will generate a more comprehensive understanding of sarcasm, its perspectives, and its underlying meanings.

2. Data Collection

Data collection methods are used by researchers to gather information and include interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. The documentation method, in particular, involves collecting data from existing documents. By using this technique, data collection can be more easily observed because the data is consistent, recorded, and well-documented, allowing researchers to frequently refer to and access data sources to avoid misunderstandings and misinterpretations.

To collect data, the researcher watched the film Cruella with subtitles to ensure a thorough understanding of the dialogue and characters. This approach allowed for greater focus and immersion, leading the researcher to view the film multiple times. Subsequently, the researcher gathered relevant references for analysis. The data for this study was collected using several methods, as detailed below:

- a. Watch the Movie Cruella several times
- b. Write a statement that contains elements of sarcasm.
- c. Connecting conversations with the context in the film.

3. Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis is crucial for research, involving the systematic collection, organisation, and analysis of data. (Miles B. Matthew 2014) Outline three steps: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Researchers first reduce data by identifying and categorising each data point into its respective type. Then, all data will be presented.

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

The analysis shows that Camp's theory of sarcasm can be applied to the film Cruella. The analysis identified various forms of sarcasm, including illocutionary sarcasm, sarcasm with the prefix "like," lexical sarcasm, and propositional sarcasm. The total number of sarcasms identified in the film Cruella is 24.

Table 1
Forms of Sarcasm Identified in the Film Cruella

Types of Sarcasm	Quantity	Percentage(%)
Illocutionary Sarcasm	14	58.5%
Like-prefixed Sarcasm	2	8.5%
Lexical Sarcasm	7	29%
Propositional Sarcasm	1	4%
Total	24	100%

As shown in Table 1, illocutionary sarcasm is the most prevalent type identified in Cruella, comprising 14 instances and accounting for 58.5% of the total data. This category of sarcasm is characterised by the use of verbal expressions that perform a particular communicative act or convey a specific intention beyond their literal meaning, and it is the type most frequently employed by the film's characters. Lexical sarcasm is the second most common form, with 7 occurrences (29%). This is followed by sarcasm employing the prefix like, which appears in 2 instances (8.5%). Propositional sarcasm is the least frequently observed type, occurring only once and representing 4% of the overall data.

1. Sarcasm Statements

Boy: *"Look as kunk released in the building"*

In this scene, Cruella greets her friend in a cordial manner; however, the boy's response indirectly comments on her appearance by comparing her to a skunk. This comparison alludes to Cruella's black-and-white hair, which deviates from the perceived

normative appearance of the other children. The utterance can be classified as lexical sarcasm, as the use of the term “skunk” functions as an indirect form of mockery rather than a literal description.

Manager: *“When you come in tomorrow, try and remember to bring a brain”*

This statement was uttered by Estella’s manager following an error when Estella was summoned to the manager’s office. The manager advised her to “use her common sense,” ostensibly framing the remark as constructive guidance in response to repeated mistakes. However, despite its seemingly benign surface meaning, the statement functioned as a veiled critique of Estella’s competence. Accordingly, the utterance can be categorised as illocutionary sarcasm, as it conveyed a subtly sarcastic intention rather than straightforward advice.

Baroness: *“You’re short, you’re fat, you smell like an anchovy, you’re colour blind but pretend that you aren’t”*

This statement was produced by the baroness during a meeting with her business partners. Although the partners intended to respond to her business feedback, the baroness redirected the conversation by remarking on their performance and physical appearance. The utterance can be classified as **lexical sarcasm**, as it conveys a harsh and explicit insult articulated with a controlled and steady intonation.

Cruella: *“Why don’t we work together to create some but for this old rag that you continue fill with that old hag?”*

In this scene, Cruella reunites with her old friend, Anita Darling, a reporter. During the meeting, Cruella negotiates with Anita to produce a new story that is projected to shake up the fashion world through its appearance. In this negotiation process, Cruella uses expressions such as “shabby rags” and “old hag” to belittle the Baroness and the old company where Anita worked. These utterances can be categorised as illocutionary sarcasm because Cruella indirectly insinuates and humiliates the other party while delivering them in the context of an invitation to collaborate.

Baroness: *“Gratitude for losers”*

This utterance is delivered by the Baroness in response to Estella’s expression of gratitude for a compliment on her design. Rather than accepting the thanks, the Baroness retorts that “thanks are for losers,” implying that expressions of gratitude are associated with weakness or failure and are therefore incompatible with ambition and success. As a ruthless and highly ambitious figure who will do anything to preserve her dominance in the fashion world, the Baroness rejects the use of the phrase “thank you,” which she appears to associate with inferiority. This

utterance can be categorised as an instance of lexical sarcasm, as the conventionally positive expression “thank you” is juxtaposed with the derogatory term “loser,” creating a sarcastic and demeaning effect.

Baroness: *“As soon as you’re not helpful, you’re dust”*

Estella: *“Inspiring talk, thank you.”*

In this scene, the Baroness and Estella are seated in a café, celebrating the designs Estella has produced for the Baroness’s upcoming spring collection. Although Estella is responsible for creating the designs, the Baroness appropriates them as her own, reinforcing the unequal power dynamic between employer and employee. The Baroness explicitly states that she will discard Estella once she is no longer useful, to which Estella responds with the phrase “inspiring words.” While superficially framed as a compliment, Estella’s utterance functions as sharp sarcasm, signalling her critical stance toward the Baroness’s callous remark. This exchange exemplifies illocutionary sarcasm, as Estella’s statement performs a pointed evaluative act that conveys contempt and exposes the speaker’s disregard for others beneath an ostensibly polite surface.

Cruella: *“You know what I miss? The Jasper who had a sense of humour”*

This utterance is delivered by Cruella to Jasper during a moment of conversation and playful exchange; however, Jasper does not respond with laughter. Rather than functioning as a genuine expression of nostalgia, the statement operates as a critical remark directed at Jasper. Cruella implies that Jasper has lost his former sense of humour, expressing disappointment in his changed disposition. Although the utterance is framed in a tone of apparent longing, it functions as subtle sarcasm. Accordingly, it can be categorised as **illocutionary sarcasm**, as the intended meaning diverges from the literal expression and serves to criticise Jasper for no longer possessing the sense of humour he once had.

Baroness: *“Do I pay you for opinion or your obedience?”*

This utterance is delivered by the Baroness and addressed to her assistant, whose expressed opinion diverges from the Baroness’s own position. While the statement appears rational on the surface, its underlying function is to criticise and demean the assistant, implicitly suggesting that they lack the authority to express independent opinions and are expected to comply unquestioningly with the Baroness’s directives. The utterance thus constitutes illocutionary sarcasm, conveying disparagement through an ostensibly neutral tone, reinforcing the assistant’s subordinate status and denying their legitimacy as an autonomous speaker.

Cruella: *“Wow, you’re a psycho”*

Baroness: *“Wow, how nice of you to say”*

The dialogue conveys a meaning that diverges from the speaker's actual communicative intention. When Cruella describes the Baroness as "a psychopath," the Baroness responds with "I'm glad you say that," ostensibly interpreting the remark as a compliment. However, this response does not reflect genuine appreciation; instead, it inverts the original insult through ironic reinterpretation. Given that the term psychopath carries strongly negative connotations and cannot reasonably function as praise, the Baroness's reply creates a tension between surface-level positivity and underlying hostility. This utterance, therefore, constitutes illocutionary sarcasm, as the apparent expression of approval contradicts the speaker's intended insult.

Jasper: *"I've had enough being treated like a dog"*

This statement indicates that Jasper experiences fatigue and disillusionment as a result of being treated as expendable—disrespected, devalued, and discarded once he is no longer considered useful. The expression "like a dog" conveys irritation and resentment, emphasising a sense of degradation and loss of dignity. The utterance can be classified as sarcasm marked by the prefix "like," as the comparative construction implicitly equates human treatment with that of animals, thereby underscoring Jasper's critical stance toward his mistreatment.

Artie: *"I was just reading about the puppy killer."*

Cruella: *"Oh, I do love spot"*

In this scene, Cruella visits Artie's shop to propose a collaboration. Artie expresses surprise at her arrival, as Cruella has recently been portrayed in the media as a "puppy killer" due to a coat she designed that resembles the black-and-white spotted pattern of a Dalmatian. Although the coat merely mimics the visual pattern and does not involve killing dogs, the label has generated public outrage. Cruella responds to Artie by stating that she simply likes the Dalmatian's spotted pattern. This utterance can be classified as illocutionary sarcasm, as it functions as a sharp, provocative remark that reframes the accusation and elicits a more subtly insulting response.

John: *"Should be a memorable night tonight, Baroness"*

Baroness: *"Indeed, should"*

This statement is delivered by John, the Baroness's assistant, on the evening of the Baroness's formal gala. At this point in the narrative, Cruella has already devised her plan for revenge, a plan of which John is fully aware. Consequently, when John tells the Baroness that the night will be "unforgettable," the utterance functions on two levels. Although it appears neutral and courteous on the surface, it carries an implicit, ironic meaning that contrasts sharply with the Baroness's expectations. For this reason, the statement can be classified as illocutionary sarcasm, as the intended meaning diverges from the literal interpretation of the utterance.

Horace: *“That dog is like a son to me, you’re dead.”*

This utterance is produced by Horace at the moment of his arrest by the Baroness’s guards, during which his dog, Wink, appears to bite one of the guards on the nose. Horace subsequently states that the dog is “like his own child,” a remark that reflects the length and emotional closeness of their relationship, as they have been together for many years and regard one another as family. This statement can be categorised as sarcasm, introduced by the comparative marker 'like', as it explicitly draws a comparison between a dog and a human child. Although the utterance is phrased in a seemingly positive and affectionate manner, its implied meaning relies on the obvious impossibility of a biological parent–child relationship between humans and animals.

Baroness: *“Where is she?”*

Anita: *“Didn’t you just to ask for her dead?”*

In this scene, the Baroness encounters Anita at her party and inquires about Cruella’s whereabouts. Although the Baroness poses the question as if Anita possesses such knowledge, the inquiry is contextually incongruous, given that she has just publicly toasted Cruella’s death. Anita’s response “Didn’t you just toast to her death?”—functions as a critical and sarcastic remark that exposes this contradiction. While the utterance is phrased as a question, its illocutionary force is not to seek information but to highlight the irrationality and hypocrisy of the Baroness’s behaviour. Therefore, the statement exemplifies illocutionary sarcasm, as its surface form appears casual and neutral, yet its intended meaning conveys reproach and irony.

Cruella: *“I hate to ruin your party, but I came to evict you.”*

In this scene, the Baroness and Cruella meet at the Baroness’s gala. Cruella begins by stating that she hates to ruin the Baroness’s party, a remark that appears polite and expresses apparent concern or regret. However, this statement is immediately contradicted by her subsequent declaration that she has come to remove the Baroness from the event. The contrast between the ostensibly courteous opening and the overtly hostile intention that follows reveals Cruella’s insincerity. Therefore, this utterance can be classified as illocutionary sarcasm, as the surface meaning suggests politeness while the intended meaning conveys confrontation and dismissal.

Cruella: *“Oh, you’re sweet and naïve, but mostly sweet”*

This phrase is uttered by Cruella and addressed to Jasper. On the surface, Cruella appears to compliment Jasper by characterising him as sweet and naïve—qualities that conventionally connote kindness and innocence. In this sense, the utterance may initially be interpreted as positive. However, the statement is delivered with a

sarcastic tone, which alters its pragmatic force. Rather than functioning as a straightforward compliment, the phrase implies that Jasper's kindness and innocence are excessive, thereby introducing a subtle critique. Consequently, this utterance can be classified as illocutionary sarcasm: although it takes the form of praise, the expression "too sweet" carries an implicit negative evaluation that undermines the literal meaning.

Baroness: *"Let me give you some advice, if you need to talk about power you don't have it"*

This statement is uttered by the Baroness and directed toward Cruella during their initial interaction at the Baroness's party. Although it is delivered in a serious and composed manner, the utterance conveys sharp sarcasm, implicitly asserting the Baroness's sense of dominance and her belief that she alone holds the authority to act without constraint. The statement can therefore be classified as illocutionary sarcasm, as its intended meaning directly contradicts its literal expression.

Cruella: *"From the very beginning, I realized I saw the world differently than everyone else"*

These words are uttered by Cruella as she reflects on her troubled life, marked by her orphaned childhood. In this moment of self-realisation, she acknowledges her inability to become a "normal" person, as her mother had hoped, due to her fundamentally different way of perceiving the world. The phrase "from the beginning" underscores this long-standing divergence in perspective and is delivered with a sarcastic tone. This utterance exemplifies propositional sarcasm, as the intended meaning contrasts with the literal expression of the statement.

Cruella: *"I am not sweet Estella, try as I might, I never was. I am Cruella born brilliant, born bad, and a little bit mad."*

The dialogue is delivered by Cruella in a moment of self-reflection after she has fully embraced the identity of Cruella, abandoning her former self as Estella. In this utterance, she employs lexemes with predominantly negative connotations; however, she uses them ironically to foreground and affirm her self-concept. The juxtaposition of descriptors such as "brilliant," "bad," and "crazy" within a single utterance constitutes a form of lexical sarcasm, exemplifying the deliberate inversion of evaluative meanings to construct identity.

Estella: *"You killed my mother."*

Baroness: *"You are going to have to be more specific, who exactly?"*

In this scene, Estella confronts the Baroness with the revelation that the Baroness was responsible for her mother's death. The Baroness responds by stating, "You need to be more specific," a remark that implies a habitual disregard for acts of violence, as though murder were so commonplace to her that further clarification is

required. Although the utterance is delivered with neutral intonation, its pragmatic force functions as an insult rather than a genuine request for information. Therefore, this statement exemplifies illocutionary sarcasm, as the speaker's intended meaning directly contradicts the literal interpretation of the utterance.

Cruella: *"There are five stages of grief: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance. Well, I'd like to add one more. Revenge"*

The dialogue is delivered by Cruella as a moment of self-reflection on her circumstances. She references the widely recognised five stages of grief—denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance—but deliberately introduces an additional stage, revenge. This addition departs from the established psychological framework, as revenge is not conventionally understood as part of the grieving process. For Cruella, however, revenge functions as a coping mechanism rather than a form of emotional healing. This intentional and ironic deviation from accepted discourse signals a sarcastic subversion of a general truth, thereby positioning the utterance within the category of lexical sarcasm.

Baroness: *"I hope for your sake, she is hidden in your coat"*

Baroness uttered these words to her guards while searching for Cruella. Although the sentence appears to express sympathy or concern, it is delivered with a coercive and threatening undertone rather than genuine hope. Despite its polite, ostensibly empathetic surface, the utterance functions as veiled sarcasm or an implicit threat. Because the literal meaning of the sentence diverges from the speaker's intended meaning, the utterance can be classified as illocutionary sarcasm, in which the expressed illocutionary force fails to align with the speaker's true communicative intent.

Baroness: *"Go and get your dry-up, desiccated little brain working."*

Baroness delivered this remark to Cruella while reviewing her designs. After evaluating all the submissions, the Baroness expressed dissatisfaction with every design. Consequently, she instructed Cruella to "drain your dry little brain," employing a sarcastic tone. This utterance functions not only as an insult but also as an exaggerated lexical choice that implies intellectual inadequacy and an inability to think creatively. Because the expression conveys mockery and disparagement through its specific word choice rather than through a reversal of propositional meaning, it can be classified as an instance of lexical sarcasm.

Artie: *"I like to say that 'normal' is the cruellest insult of them all, and at least I never get that."*

The statement is uttered by Artie, a clothing store owner whose unconventional appearance distinguishes him from others. He asserts that the term "normal"

constitutes the cruellest insult, despite its generally positive or neutral connotation in common usage. For Artie, however, “normal” acquires a negative evaluative meaning because his appearance deviates from societal norms; consequently, he is rarely described as “normal” and is instead more frequently labelled “unusual.” This reversal of semantic value demonstrates lexical sarcasm, as the word is used to convey irony, critique, or ridicule, contradicting its conventional meaning.

2. Discussion

2.1. *Sarcasm as Rhetorical Strategy and Cultural Critique in Cruella (2021)*

An analysis of sarcasm in the film *Cruella* (2021) reveals that it functions as a central rhetorical, narrative, and ideological device rather than merely a stylistic feature. Sarcasm enhances the film’s comedic tone while also serving as a mechanism for character development, social critique, and resistance to dominant cultural norms. Through sarcastic dialogue, exaggerated performance, and ironic visual aesthetics, the film constructs Cruella de Vil as a complex protagonist whose identity is shaped through defiance, self-awareness, and opposition to hegemonic expectations. Sarcasm in *Cruella* thus transcends humour, becoming a mode of communication that reflects psychological defence, cultural rebellion, and the politics of identity formation.

From the outset, the film establishes sarcasm as an intrinsic part of Cruella’s worldview. The protagonist’s voice-over narration, delivered with sharp irony and self-mockery, immediately signals a refusal to conform to sentimental or morally straightforward storytelling. This narrative choice positions sarcasm as a framing device, guiding the audience’s interpretation of events through a lens of scepticism and critical distance. Rather than relying solely on vulnerability to elicit sympathy, the film uses sarcasm to foster intimacy between Cruella and the audience, encouraging viewers to align with her critical perspective on society. In this sense, sarcasm operates as a rhetorical bridge, transforming the audience from passive spectators into complicit observers of social hypocrisy.

Cruella’s sarcastic wit also plays a significant role in shaping her identity. Throughout the film, sarcasm serves as a verbal and performative shield, masking emotional vulnerability and protecting her from disappointment, loss, and betrayal. This aligns with scholarly interpretations of sarcasm as a defensive communicative strategy, often employed to maintain psychological distance while asserting intellectual or emotional superiority. However, Cruella complicates this notion by framing sarcasm not solely as avoidance but as empowerment. Cruella’s cutting remarks and ironic detachment enable her to navigate hostile environments, particularly the elitist and exclusionary world of high fashion, where sincerity is often punished and conformity rewarded.

Importantly, the film uses sarcasm to subvert the conventional Disney-villain

archetype. Traditional villains are frequently characterised by exaggerated evil, moral clarity, and narrative distance from the audience. In contrast, Cruella's sarcasm humanises her while simultaneously destabilising moral binaries. Her dark humour and ironic self-awareness invite the audience to reconsider the very notion of villainy, suggesting that social marginalisation, systemic injustice, and personal trauma contribute significantly to her transformation. Sarcasm thus becomes a narrative tool that reframes Cruella's actions not as inherent cruelty but as a response to oppressive structures and repeated exclusions.

The use of sarcasm in Cruella also operates as a form of social and cultural critique. Cruella's sharp remarks often target institutions of authority, including the fashion industry, class hierarchy, and the myth of meritocracy. The Baroness, as a symbol of elite power and aesthetic absolutism, is frequently contrasted with Cruella's irreverent sarcasm, which exposes the hollowness of the Baroness's moral and artistic superiority. Through sarcastic exchanges and visual irony, the film critiques the hypocrisy of systems that celebrate originality while simultaneously enforcing rigid norms. Sarcasm, in this context, functions as a destabilising force that reveals contradictions embedded within dominant cultural narratives.

Beyond dialogue, Cruella extends sarcasm into its visual and auditory design, creating a cohesive aesthetic of irony. The punk- inspired soundtrack, exaggerated costume designs, and theatrically staged confrontations collectively reinforce the film's sarcastic tone. These elements do not merely complement the dialogue but actively participate in the film's rhetorical strategy. For example, the dramatic unveiling of Cruella's fashion statements often borders on parody, using excess and spectacle to mock the seriousness of high fashion culture. This visual sarcasm mirrors Cruella's verbal wit, demonstrating how sarcasm operates across multiple semiotic levels within the film.

Sarcasm in Cruella also serves as a form of resistance, particularly in relation to societal expectations around gender, class, and professionalism. Cruella's refusal to adhere to norms of politeness, emotional restraint, and feminine modesty is consistently articulated through sarcastic defiance. Her tone challenges the expectation that women, especially those from marginalised backgrounds, must remain grateful, agreeable, and invisible. Instead, sarcasm allows Cruella to assert her presence forcefully, reclaiming agency in spaces that seek to silence or discipline her. In this way, sarcasm becomes a performative act of resistance, transforming speech into political expression.

However, the film's reliance on sarcasm also raises questions about authenticity and identity. Estella's transformation into Cruella is marked not only by a change in appearance but by a noticeable shift in communicative style. Sarcasm evolves from a situational response into her dominant mode of expression, blurring the boundary between defence mechanism and identity performance. This transformation

invites critical reflection on whether Cruella represents Estella's "true self" or a constructed persona shaped by trauma, anger, and resistance. Sarcasm, while empowering, may also limit emotional openness, suggesting that rebellion comes at the cost of vulnerability.

This ambiguity is central to the film's thematic complexity. Rather than presenting sarcasm as an unequivocally positive trait, Cruella portrays it as both liberating and isolating. Cruella's relationships are often strained by her ironic detachment, indicating that sarcasm, while effective as a critique, can hinder genuine connection. This tension underscores the psychological cost of constant resistance and raises broader questions about the sustainability of oppositional identities within oppressive systems. Sarcasm, in this sense, becomes a double-edged sword—capable of dismantling authority while simultaneously reinforcing emotional distance.

Within the broader context of popular culture, the use of sarcasm in Cruella aligns with contemporary trends in the representation of female antiheroes. These characters frequently employ irony and wit to navigate patriarchal structures that restrict autonomy and self-expression. As noted by Nasir, Haryanti, and Sumbayak (2024), Western popular culture often complicates traditional norms by allowing female characters to articulate identity through resistance, critique oppression, and negotiate autonomy within patriarchal contexts. Sarcasm functions as a linguistic and performative strategy that enables such negotiation, allowing characters like Cruella to challenge power without fully assimilating into it.

Furthermore, the film's sarcastic tone reflects a broader cultural shift toward irony as a dominant mode of expression in late modernity. In a media landscape saturated with performativity and spectacle, sarcasm offers a means of signalling awareness and resistance to manipulation. Cruella capitalises on this cultural sensibility, positioning its protagonist as someone who understands the artificiality of the systems she inhabits and responds with exaggerated irony. This resonance with contemporary audiences reinforces the film's cultural relevance and ideological appeal.

So, sarcasm in Cruella plays a multifaceted role that extends far beyond humour. It serves as a rhetorical device, a narrative strategy, and a form of cultural resistance that shapes character identity and critiques social structures. Through sarcastic dialogue, visual irony, and performative excess, the film constructs Cruella de Vil as a rebellious figure navigating the tension between authenticity and survival. While sarcasm empowers Cruella to challenge societal expectations and assert autonomy, it also exposes the emotional costs of sustained defiance. Ultimately, Cruella demonstrates how sarcasm functions within popular culture as a powerful medium for negotiating identity, articulating resistance, and questioning the legitimacy of dominant norms.

E. CONCLUSION

In *Cruella* (2021), sarcasm operates as a central rhetorical strategy that extends far beyond ornamental dialogue or comedic relief, ultimately functioning as a defining mechanism in the film's narrative and ideological framework. From the perspective of character development, sarcasm is integral to the construction of Cruella de Vil's identity, shaping both her psychological evolution and her relationship with the social world she inhabits. Rather than merely signalling wit or humour, sarcasm becomes the primary mode through which Cruella articulates dissent, negotiates power, and performs selfhood within an environment governed by hierarchy, spectacle, and control. Her sarcastic speech patterns reveal a character who is acutely aware of social contradictions and who actively weaponises language to resist marginalisation.

Sarcasm plays a crucial role in mediating Cruella's transformation from an alienated outsider into a figure of calculated cruelty and emotional detachment. Through her sharp, ironic remarks, Cruella constructs a persona that simultaneously asserts dominance and conceals vulnerability. This dual function underscores sarcasm's psychological complexity: it allows the protagonist to shield herself from emotional exposure while projecting confidence, superiority, and intellectual acuity. In this sense, sarcasm serves as both a defensive mechanism and an instrument of self-fashioning. The film suggests that Cruella's growing reliance on sarcasm parallels her increasing cynicism, as her wit gradually hardens into a mode of interaction that prioritises control over connection.

Moreover, Cruella demonstrates that sarcasm is deeply embedded in the film's social critique, particularly in its portrayal of the fashion industry and elite culture. Cruella's sarcastic observations and confrontational humour expose the hypocrisy, artificiality, and moral emptiness of high society. By ridiculing authority figures and aesthetic conventions, she challenges the legitimacy of the power structures that exclude and exploit individuals deemed insufficiently conformist. Sarcasm thus functions as a subversive discourse, destabilising the norms that govern taste, success, and respectability. Cruella's refusal to adopt deferential language positions her as a disruptive presence who rejects the expectation of silence or compliance imposed upon those at the margins.

Importantly, the film frames sarcasm as a form of resistance that is both empowering and corrosive. While Cruella's wit enables her to reclaim agency and assert autonomy, it also contributes to her emotional isolation and moral ambiguity. Sarcasm becomes a double-edged rhetorical device: it empowers the protagonist to dismantle oppressive systems while simultaneously reinforcing her detachment from empathy and relational intimacy. This tension complicates any straightforward reading of sarcasm as purely liberatory, instead presenting it as a strategy shaped by social exclusion and personal trauma.

Finally, Cruella offers a nuanced depiction of sarcasm as a multifaceted narrative device that enriches the film's thematic depth. Sarcasm functions as a marker of intelligence, outsider status, and ideological resistance, while also charting the protagonist's descent into cynicism and emotional guardedness. By foregrounding sarcasm as both a sword and a shield, the film invites viewers to reflect critically on the intersections of identity, rebellion, and social power. Ultimately, Cruella's strategic use of sarcasm deepens the narrative's complexity, transforming wit into a lens through which broader questions of self- construction and resistance are explored.

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